

Sr^{2+} and Pb^{2+} did not produce any colour with BN. No change in colour was observed in case of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} . BN produced orange or yellow colour with ATC on spot plate, with the evolution of violet gas during trituration while a white precipitate with a yellow solution were produced when their aqueous solutions were mixed in a test tube. However, when the reactants were brought in close contact in a glass capillary at 30° , a pink colour immediately appeared at the BN-ATC junction. The pink colour rapidly moved towards ATC and portion of the capillary containing ATC became pink within 5 min. The pink colour started to change to orange-yellow or yellow after 20 min. A yellow product formed on trituration of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ with BN converted into red within 5 min while a dark brown precipitate was produced in solution. NO_3^- and Zn^{2+} both gave yellow products in the solid-state but in solution they gave white precipitate. In solid-state, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ gave brown product which change to red on keeping at room temperature whereas in solution only a brown precipitate was obtained.

Of all the ions which gave coloured products with BN, I^- produced the largest boundary length towards test material, leading to selective detection of I^- . I^- can be distinguished from NO_3^- , VO_3^- , Br^- , CrO_4^{2-} and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ on the basis of the boundary length at 30° or 50° . The orange and yellow product boundaries formed at 50° after 30 min by $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (4 mm towards reagent) and CrO_4^{2-} (1 mm towards test material) moved in opposite directions with different rates. Thus $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and CrO_4^{2-} can be sharply distinguished. Likewise, Fe^{3+} can be distinguished from Cu^{2+} and Cr^{3+} on the basis of the length and the direction of the product boundary. $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ both producing blue product at BN-test material junction can be distinguished easily on the basis of the boundary length at 50° .

The length of the product zone increased with time, temperature and the concentration of the reagent. Thus, an enhanced selectivity can be attained by performing capillary solid-state spot-test with lower concentration of the reagent or by reducing the reaction time. As a result, I^- and NCS^- can be selectively detected in presence of the other ions by using 1% BN at 30° . Furthermore, 1% BN can be utilised for the specific detection of NCS^- which formed a product zone of 14 mm towards the test material at 30° after 30 min. None of the ions except I^- gave any colour, which produced a yellow thin ring at the interface of the reactants.

Glass-wool plug modified capillary solid-state spot-test technique offers more effective alternative for the selective or even specific detection of NCS^- . For this purpose, a glass wool plug of 4 mm was introduced between the reagent and the test material in glass capillary. None of the ions tested gave any colour either at glass wool-reagent or glass wool-test material junction at 40° upto 4 h except NCS^-

which produced yellow boundary at glass wool-test material junction after 1 h, which may thus be specifically detected. Thus the presence of 5 or 10% NCS^- was successfully detected in the mixture containing 95% Br^- , VO_3^- , $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, CrO_4^{2-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ or 90% NO_3^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, S^{2-} , Zn^{2+} and Fe^{2+} by observing yellow colour at glass-wool-test material junction at 40° after 2 h.

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly thankful to the Chairman, Department of Applied Chemistry, Z. H. College of Engineering and Technology for facilities.

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Conductometric and Enthalpimetric Determination of Saccharin in Acetone

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Manuscript received 6 January 1988, revised 6 July 1988, accepted 13 September 1988

SACCHARIN is a weak acid with $\text{p}K_a$ 11.6 and finds use as an artificial sweetener. Different methods are suggested for its determination¹. The official recommended methods² use titrations with alkali in hot aqueous or alcoholic solutions. No work has been reported for the determination of saccharin in nonaqueous solvents, hence, this study was undertaken. The paper describes conductometric and enthalpimetric titrations methods of estimation of saccharin in acetone medium using two different titrants. Optimum conditions for its determination are standardised.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Saccharin (B.P.) was recrystallised twice from alcohol, dried (m.p. 223°) and its purity checked by tlc. Acetone and isopropanol were purified by method reported earlier³. Potassium hydroxide in isopropanol (alc. KOH) and tetra-*n*-butylammonium hydroxide (*t*-Bu₄NOH) in toluene-methanol were prepared as described earlier⁴.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION

Sl. no.	Wt. of saccharin titrated mg	Wt. found with alc. KOH*				Wt. found with t-Bu ₄ NOH*			
		Cond.	Error	Enth.	Error	Cond.	Error	Enth.	Error
1.	0.46	0.488	+5.8	0.488	+5.0	0.448	-2.6	0.408	-11.3
2.	0.92	0.908	-2.8	0.948	+2.6	0.897	-3.8	0.884	-5.0
3.	1.84	1.812	-1.9	1.852	+0.5	1.917	+5.0	1.904	+3.5
4.	3.68	3.744	+1.7	3.664	-0.6	3.754	+2.1	3.742	+1.5
5.	5.52	5.475	-1.0	5.456	+1.2	5.413	+1.9	5.504	-0.4
6.	7.36	7.287	-1.0	7.390	-0.9	7.616	+3.4	7.616	+3.4
7.	9.20	9.820	+1.2	9.098	-1.1	9.452	+2.7	9.452	+2.7
8.	11.04	10.780	-2.8	10.686	-2.2	11.856	+2.9	11.288	+2.2
9.	12.88	12.450	-3.4	12.450	-3.4	13.828	+3.5	13.600	+5.6
10.	14.72	14.124	-4.1	14.080	-4.7	16.184	+9.0	16.320	+10.8
11.	16.56	15.796	-4.7	15.703	-5.8	17.680	+6.8	17.680	+6.8
12.	18.40	16.911	-8.7	17.097	-7.1	20.586	+11.6	20.740	+12.5

* Method: Cond. = conductometric, Enth. = enthalpimetric.

The conductometric titrations were carried out using a Naina digital conductometer with an accuracy of $\pm 1 \mu\Omega^{-1}$. The conductivity cell was conditioned in acetone before use. Enthalpimetric titrations were carried out in an insulated beaker and catalytic polymerisation of acetone was used to detect the end-point⁵.

Procedure: All titrations were carried out as reported earlier⁴. Benzoic acid (A.R.) in acetone was used to standardise both alc. KOH and t-Bu₄NOH and the end-points were determined graphically.

Results and Discussion

Choice of proper titrant: Titration curves for conductometric titrations (not shown) did not show sharp breaks and so the end-point was obtained by extrapolation. The enthalpimetric titration curves showed a sharp break (not shown) at the end-point with a sudden increase of temperature due to polymerisation of anhydrous acetone with a slight excess of the titrant. The results obtained with both the titrants (Table 1) reveal that alc. KOH is a better titrant than t-Bu₄NOH.

Effect of dilution: A constant weight of saccharin was titrated by both the methods at different dilutions. The total volume was varied from 15 to 40 ml in steps. There was no noticeable effect of dilution observed within the limits studied.

Effect of concentration: A stock solution of saccharin in acetone (1.85 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared and different volumes of these solutions (1–20 ml) were diluted to 20 ml with acetone and titrated by these methods and the results are presented in Table 1. Saccharin in the range 1.8–10 mg (0.09 – 0.5 mg ml^{-1}) can be determined with an error less than 2% by conductometric method and in the same range with an error less than 1.2% by enthalpimetric method. The mean and standard deviations were found to be 0.10 and 0.14 for conductometric and 0.09 and 0.098 for enthalpimetric method, respectively.

Both the methods are simple, fast and do not require any sophisticated instruments. The results are reproducible. The advantages of determining saccharin in nonaqueous solvent over aqueous methods are that saccharin is highly soluble in cold acetone and much smaller amount can be determined. However, saccharin is not soluble in cold water so heating or addition of alcohol is required to dissolve it for its determination in aqueous medium.

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Photometric Determination of Benzidine as Azo Dye in Traces using Salicylic Acid

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Manuscript received 9 March 1987, revised 28 June 1988, accepted 13 September 1988

BENZIDINE is normally determined just like other aromatic amines¹ and its MAK value could not be established due to high toxicity². The present paper describes a photometric method for its deter-